

crops at PES also were severely damaged. We correlated GLH incidence with RTV infection based on light trap catches and field scores.

A modified Robinson light trap with a 120-watt M.V. lamp was operated from 1800 to 2400 h. GLH catch and

RTV infection were recorded daily. GLH field infestation was recorded 30 d after transplanting (DT) and RTV infection 45 DT on TKM9 in sornavari, CO 43 in samba (Jul-Aug to Dec-Jan), and ADT36 in navarai (Dec-Jan to Apr-May).

GLH were present all year, but the population peaked on 9 Jul 1984, when 36,000 GLH were trapped. Field counts confirmed the trend (see table). Level of RTV infection followed a similar pattern, peaking in Jul, and gradually declining from Aug to Oct. *J*

Changes in the key enzymes of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn

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Sheath blight disease caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn is a serious problem in India. Phenyl acetic acid and its hydroxy isomers have been identified as the major phytotoxic metabolites of several isolates of *R. solani*. Most of these metabolites are produced during the degradative metabolism of phenylalanine and tyrosine. We studied the involvement of the enzymes phenylalanine ammonia lyase (PAL) and tyrosine ammonia lyase (TAL) in phenylalanine and tyrosine degradation.

Five *R. solani* isolates with different

Cinnamic acid (μg)/mg protein per h
p-Coumaric acid (μg)/mg protein per h

PAL and TAL activities of 5 differentially virulent *R. solani* isolates, Cuddalore, India.

virulence were inoculated in 20 ml of Czapek's (Dox) broth for 7 d at 25°C and grew as stationary cultures. PAL and TAL activities of the cell-free mycelial extracts were assayed.

There was no relationship between TAL activity of the isolates and their virulence. However, there appeared to be a relationship between virulence and PAL activity (see figure). *J*

Management of seedborne *Drechslera oryzae* of rice with plant extracts

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We identified plant extracts to control *Drechslera oryzae* (Breda de Haan) Subram and Jain.

Extracts of *Azadirachta indica* bark, *Eupatorium cannabinum* leaf, *Allium sativum* cloves, *Acorus calamus* rhizome, *Piper nigrum* seeds, and *Mentha piperita* leaf were prepared at 25 g each in 50 ml of distilled water by

crushing in a mortar and pestle. IR20 seeds, which have high natural infection of *D. oryzae*, were soaked in the filtrate for 24 h before sowing. Dry infected seeds and seeds soaked in distilled water were used as control treatments. Percentage of *D. oryzae*-infected seeds was recorded using the blotter method, and germination and seedling vigor were assessed by the paper towel method.

M. piperita and *A. sativum* extracts significantly reduced seed infection by *D. oryzae*, and treated seeds had significantly higher viability (see table). Extract-treated seeds produced seedlings with longer shoots and roots than those in the untreated check. *J*

Efficacy of plant extracts as seed treatments for controlling *Drechslera oryzae*, Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Extract	Seeds infected with <i>D. oryzae</i> (%)	Seed germination (%)	Seedling vigor	
			Root length (cm)	Shoot length (cm)
<i>Allium sativum</i>	11 (18.92)	81 (69.11)	20.7	9.8
<i>Mentha piperita</i>	11 (18.92)	85 (69.04)	20.2	9.7
<i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i>	72 (53.35)	64 (54.14)	18.8	8.8
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	73 (58.92)	64 (54.14)	18.6	8.8
<i>Acorus calamus</i>	75 (60.24)	65 (53.14)	18.5	8.6
<i>Piper nigrum</i>	76 (60.86)	63 (52.58)	18.2	8.6
Seeds soaked in water for 24 h	72 (58.35)	13 (58.92)	16.3	8.6
Infected dry seeds	85 (61.33)	43 (38.43)	15.3	7.5
CD (P=0.01)	9	5	3.55	1.13

^aTransformed values in parentheses.